

NOSOCOMIAL INFECTION ASSOCIATED WITH THE MECHANISM OF BACTERIAL RESISTANCE

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Abstract

Hospital infections are related to the mechanism of bacterial resistance. The objective of this study is to observe which factors lead to bacteria becoming resistant, and the importance of measures to control and prevent hospital infections. The bibliographic research was done on the history of infections, findings, the current scenario and the posture of health professionals in this context. It was concluded that professionals and population should have hygiene habits, avoid self-medication and use antibiotics in the correct dosage for resistance control.

Keywords: Infection. Resistance. Bacterium. Hospital.

Introduction

This study has as its theme hospital infection and the relationship of this process with the mechanism of bacterial resistance. In parallel, this process can be alleviated with preventive measures through hygiene and adequate use of antibiotics.

The questions that supported the work are:

What is the relationship of nosocomial infections with the mechanism of bacterial resistance?

What measures should be taken to prevent and control bacteria that become resistant and the hospital infection process?

When a patient is hospitalized, especially in critical situations, such as surgeries, admissions to the Intensive Care Unit (ICU), or similar cases, there is a high possibility that the patient will develop a hospital infection. This infection can be caused by some bacteria that triggers a resistance mechanism, making healing difficult. Hence the importance of conducting an investigation into the development of this process and what measures can be taken for proper control.

Eliete Batista Moura and others bring, through the Ministry of Health, the definition of hospital infection:

The Ministry of Health (MS), in Ordinance No. 2,616 of 05/12/1998, defines hospital infection as the infection acquired after the patient's admission to the hospital unit and that manifests itself during hospitalization or after discharge, when it can be related with hospitalization or hospital procedures (ELIETE BATISTA MOURA, et al, 2007, p. 416).

In this context, the investigation of the hospital infection process and how it relates to resistant bacteria is very relevant to discuss, encourage and promote actions to control the problem.

The methodology used to achieve the proposed objectives was a bibliographical research carried out through detailed analysis of scientific articles published in specialized databases.

This article was based on works carried out by authors such as: Da Mata Abegg and Da Silva (2011), Eliete Batista Moura and others (2007), Fontana (2006), Nogueira and others (2009), Oliveira and Silva (2008), Oliveira, Damasceno and Ribeiro (2009) and Santos de Queiroz (2004).

Theoretical Reference

The concern with infections arising from surgical processes or caused by microorganisms has always been present throughout human history.

Fontana (2006) reports that since the Middle Ages there has been talk of contamination and infectious diseases. In the Renaissance, with the creation of the press, it made possible the dissemination of scientific works, tests and experiments carried out by scientists at the time, such as vaccines and the discovery of microorganisms.

Over time, there were discoveries of contamination and infections caused by surgery. It was also later discovered the importance of hygiene care and use of equipment to avoid contamination such as masks, gloves, coats, proper hygiene and hand washing.

Later, with the advancement of Science, it made knowledge about microorganisms, including bacteria, possible. Such beings have different formats and are present in the most varied environments. They can act in a beneficial or harmful way, in the latter case, seen as pathogens. These beings are in all environments, in the digestive system of some animals, including humans, acting as decomposers of organic matter and in hospitals or outside them, causing diseases, including infections.

Currently, infections are a real health problem around the world. There are several factors involved in the process that leads to an infection. These factors range from attitudes that must be changed by the community to health professionals: lack of hand washing, self-

medication and abusive use of antibiotics. In addition to this, it is also necessary to consider the invasive methods performed in health institutions as surgical processes, which can be considered a means of transmission of infections.

Hospital infection has specific technical characteristics to achieve its diagnosis, which can be considered as:

[...] that related to hospitalization, so considered when the incubation period of the pathogen causing the infection is unknown and there is no clinical evidence and/or laboratory data of infection at the time of hospitalization; or the appearance of any clinical manifestation of infection from 72 hours after admission, with the patient diagnosed with community infection and a different germ is isolated, followed by the worsening of its clinical conditions (NOGUEIRA et al, 2009, p. 97).

In a study carried out by Eliete Batista Moura et al (2007), in the ICU of a public hospital in Piauí, it was found that most hospital infections are related to the respiratory tract, representing more than 60% of cases. The estimate is based on urinary, systemic, integumentary and surgical wound infections.

The microorganisms that had the highest rate of nosocomial infection in the study were: *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas* sp, *S. aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, *Preoteus mirabilis*, *Proteus* sp and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*.

In other research conducted by Da Mata Abegg and Da Silva, they also identified *Staphylococcus epidermidis* as involved in nosocomial infections.

The most common infectious agents isolated in ICUs are *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Staphylococcus epidermidis* is present on the skin of healthy or unhealthy individuals, and can be introduced into the ICU by patients or collaborating health care members, causing opportunistic infections during and/or after invasive procedures” (DA MATA ABEGG and DA SILVA, 2011, p. 50).

Oliveira and Silva (2008) observe that *Burkholderia cepacea* or *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* can be stored in soaps, clothes and coats. This fact causes these microorganisms to be taken outside the hospital environment, triggering transmission and contamination from other environments.

The problem is very serious, knowing that certain microorganisms are able to survive in different conditions and environments. Given this fact, it is clear that hospital infections are interrelated with the mechanism that makes bacteria resistant.

The hospital environment is home to several types of microorganisms, where many people come into contact with others, whether between patients or family members. In addition, hospitalized patients undergo surgical and interventional procedures. This scenario allows bacteria to develop resistance mechanisms against different types of drugs.

Bacteria have the specialty of adapting to changes in the environment. In this context, for example, when an antibiotic is used without due moderation, it causes the bacteria to increase its exposure in relation to the drug, as a consequence, it creates the ability to become resistant to the antibiotic. This fact explains when the same drug is used again and the expected effect is not obtained, as bacterial resistance to the aforementioned antibiotic occurred.

Bacteria are able to develop specialized forms of enzymes to inactivate the expected effects of antimicrobials. As analyzed by Oliveira, Damasceno and Ribeiro (2009), when there is an increase in metabolic and reproductive rates, they can also trigger the process of bacterial resistance. A bacterium can gain resistance without having to have contact with a certain drug. This can be explained by the genetic mutation, by gene-linked transfer, related to the exchanged genetic material.

Oliveira and Silva (2008, p. 191) state that "because resistance is a complex phenomenon, it involves the microorganism, patient, antimicrobial agent, and the environment separately and/or in their interaction." Patients of all ages can develop the process of infection by microorganisms. Risk groups are the elderly and patients with compromised immune systems.

Patients with weakened immune systems, coming from surgery or in intensive care are seen as a group with a high probability of acquiring nosocomial infection caused by bacterial resistance. These patients usually stay for a longer time in the hospital unit and are exposed to treatments with antimicrobials, which in turn, fail to achieve the expected results. These drugs are weak compared to the high resistance potential of certain species of bacteria.

Bacterial resistance can originate from different processes such as the abusive use of antimicrobials by people without a medical prescription, or lack of concern with the dosages of these drugs when prescribed by specialists. In this process, the lack of moderation in the use of antimicrobials increases the selective pressure of bacteria, creating the mechanism of resistance.

Another point of great importance that can cause bacteria to become resistant is the breach of hygiene and biosafety protocols by health professionals. Acts such as not washing hands, wearing lab coats in public environments, outside the hospital environment, means that the bacteria can trigger a process of resistance and spread.

The trilogy represented by the indiscriminate use of antimicrobials, few hand washing by health professionals and the weak immune system of the hospitalized patient, makes bacterial resistance even more potent, constituting a serious health problem in various parts of the planet.

Importantly, the risk of occurrence of hospital infections related to bacterial resistance is very high.

Hospitals, especially those with an intensive care unit (ICU), operating room, pediatric units, neonatal nursery, medical and/or surgical clinic, in which patients are treated with antimicrobials, represent a "habitat" that harbors bacteria that they can become resistant to those drugs" (SANTOS DE QUEIROZ, 2004, p. 65).

Therefore, measures to prevent cases of resistance should be taken through hand hygiene, surfaces and instruments used in hospitals, awareness of the population about the inappropriate use of self-medication and, by specialists, on the proper prescription of antimicrobials in accordance with the needs of each patient. It is also essential to create and maintain a database with files of patients who were infected, types of bacteria, hospital stay and training of professionals on the subject.

Hospital hygiene protocols determine that the objects and articles used must be disinfected and sterilized, but due to the precarious situations of public health in Brazil and other places, many utensils are only disinfected, thus contributing to the increase in the seriousness of the problem.

Health professionals should pay special attention to hand washing. This act can help to reduce bacterial resistance levels, aiming at its control. Oliveira, Damasceno and Ribeiro (2009, p. 449) report that the "factors indicated for poor hand hygiene are: lack of access to sinks, insufficient time for professionals, products that irritate the skin, lack of knowledge about their impact on prevention of infections." In this sense, in addition to the availability of hand hygiene products, it is necessary to develop guidance for professionals to take this measure as a standard and for constant use.

Discussions

A measure considered valid is the performance of antibiogram tests that clearly determine the amount of antibiotics to be prescribed for each specific patient. With this strategy, the rates of indiscriminate use of these drugs may decrease.

It is also worth considering the isolation of patients diagnosed with nosocomial infection and with bacteria with high potential for resistance. This isolation will reduce contact with family members and the health team. Circulation of microorganisms in this case will also be reduced.

In many cases, the patient looks to the hospital for a place to treat and cure illnesses, but it is in this scenario that thousands of antibiotic-resistant bacteria are housed. When such a patient recovers from the illness that initially took him to the health unit, he will eventually also have to treat some consequence of the bacteria that has become resistant.

The costs for hospital infections are high. It is necessary the constant action of committees to combat hospital infections and in the absence of these, they must be implemented as a matter of urgency. Also essential is the guidance and awareness of the population regarding the use of antibiotics, which should be done in moderation. Another important point is to carry out simple habits, washing and sanitizing your hands constantly during the day.

Conclusions

With this work, it was possible to observe a growing use of antibiotics to combat microorganisms, especially bacteria. This use most often occurs without prior knowledge of the amount of medication needed for each specific patient.

The dissemination of data on nosocomial infection is still very small. Many healthcare institutions do not have designated hospital infection control committees.

To combat hospital resistance it is necessary to unite the hospital team. Physicians, nurses and assistants should be aware of the importance of asepsis, constant hand washing, and the use of alcohol-gel. Laboratory technicians must take measures to control the spread of new species that can affect hospitals, managements must be alert for decision-making to combat bacterial resistance.

It may also be necessary to isolate patients carrying a potentially highly resistant microorganism. Isolation reduces the patient's contact with professionals and family members, and can also reduce the spread of bacteria.

It is also necessary to perform antibiogram tests to determine the specificity and exact amount of medication to be prescribed for each patient. It is also of great importance that the population and the health team make moderate use of antimicrobials.

Prevention and precautionary measures such as hygienic measures, raising awareness for health professionals and the population regarding the proliferation of bacteria and the resistance mechanism are key initiatives. It is also necessary to create public policies for intervention and control of bacterial resistance and hospital infections.

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